

Descriptive Assessments of Business Score Card (BSC) Implementation Practices on Firm Performance of SMEs, Manufacturing, Textile, and Apparel Industries in Ethiopia

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Abstract – The objectives and the aim of this study that titled the descriptive statistics of BSC implementation practice with Firm Performance the Mediating role of new product development practice with Positive effect of Firm SMEs performance in Textile and Apparel Manufacturing industries in Ethiopia that provides firms with opportunity to grow, and enhance in BSC dynamism in the Financial performance, Learning and Growth, Business Process and Customer Perspective activities in Manufacturing industry in SMEs and the findings that showed that the Descriptive effect of BSC activities practice on firm Performance in textile and Apparel industry in Ethiopia. However, the Business Score card (BSC) implementation practices is much stronger in influence the export performance that affect BSC through Financial performance, Learning and Growth, Business Process and Customer Perspective activities in Manufacturing industry in SMEs, it designed with Descriptive Statistics to distribute for 390 respondents, and the questionnaires to be distributed from Workers, CEO, CMO, CFO, CCO and from the managers of manufacturing textile and Apparel Industry of SMEs to be the targeted area of data sampling to the study of Descriptive design and effect in Ethiopia. Hence, this study basically increased the knowledge regarding of the factors that affect BSC practice and implementation practices the firm Performance, especially in manufacturing textile and Apparel Industry SMEs Ethiopia.

Keywords: BSC, Financial Performance, Business Process, Customer Perspectives, Learning and Growth perspectives and Firm Performance, SMEs.

1. FIRM PERFORMANCE

Abdul Adis and Jublee, (2020) Firm performance has become a significant concern for today's diverse business owners, managers, and accountants in many countries (Chelliah et al., 2023). Bahiaa et al. (2019) stated that a firm's performance indicates an organisations' capacity and willingness to achieve the outcomes that it has previously established, as well as gauges the organisations' performance in accomplishing its survival and growth goals (Tesfa, 2023). The major target of all enterprises should be aligned with their goals and objectives to achieve maximum profit (Tesfa, 2023; Farooq et al., 2021).

2. FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE

Thuong & Singh, (2023) The Financial Performance is one element of the BSC. when considering an enterprise's performance of SMEs manufacturing industries of Financial Performance perspectives that reveals a significant positive relationship with performance of SMEs with its strategy implementation through the use of the BSC and it incorporating financial and nonfinancial measures of SMEs (Yuliana and Kristiana, 2021) and these factors that support the enhancement of the SMEs performance through motivational factors and Financial Performance that includes Rate On Investments, accounts payable &

receivable, earnings per share & that operating expenses of SMEs manufacturing textile industry (Ayalu et al., 2022).

Financial Performance of SMEs to be predicted that how the strategies of Manufacturing textile industries of the implementation, execution will impacted the business profitability of SMEs, growth & shareholder value of SMEs (Yaskun et al., 2023). Therefore, the Financial Performance helps businesses to determine their profits and financial goals effectively (Girma et al., 2022). The overall financial position considers profitability, revenue growth, increased sales, as well as revenue generated by each customer per visit (Thuong & Singh, 2023).

3. BUSINESS PROCESS

The Business Process is also a part of the BSC to Thuong & Singh, (2023) is the positive outcomes that resulting from the adopting internal business processes such as the BSC it include the functionality of business operations perspectives, reworks & reductions in operational costs (Alhamami et al., 2023). Several researches has says a widening the incorporation and a coverage of the total internal business process and it suggests that a more comprehensive business system of SMEs performance can contribute to the long-term success of an enterprise (Yaskun et al., 2023).

This business process that facilitates the identification of key processes that guides the development of the most suitable measurements and enabling them to grow to meet more expectations of both customers process (Girma et al., 2022) and shareholders alike can be thereby that enhancing the enterprise's financial business process position (Yaskun et al., 2023). An additional focus is required by SMEs on various issues such as order processing, manufacturing, Services delivery and product (Thuong & Singh, 2023) and to satisfy customers' needs & wants, in SMEs can be identify adopted new internal business processes opposed to only making high improvement to their existing business processes (Yuliana and Kristiana, 2021) and Product development, manufacturing processes, operations, delivery, and after-sales activities must be considered (Thuong & Singh, 2023).

4. LEARNING AND GROWTH PERSPECTIVES

(Kaplan & Norton, 1996) suggested that Learning and Growth perspectives within SMEs is another part of the BSC organizational benefits that relative to the learning & growth outcomes of the BSC in business industries include business research and organizational development, SMEs employee morale, employees innovative performance contributions (Yuliana and Kristiana, 2021), and it identifying the multifaceted means of learning and growth are imperative to provide the employee satisfaction to matches the ever demanding & changing requirements of an business enterprise's of SMEs (Yaskun et al., 2023) and to gain a competitive advantage in the global business economy of human resource managers and leaders of company have begun to use more modern methods that focus on human capital development of SMEs performance (Girma et al., 2022) and BSC business performance indicators rather than on traditional management methods that focus and reducing business costs that increasing efficiency to be controlling employees satisfactions of SMEs of manufacturing industries (Thuong & Singh, 2023) and LG perspectives are recognised as a core factor in achieving the successful industry implementation of the Business Sectors that assists the employees in learning new business skills and management information systems process of SMEs (Kaplan & Norton, 1996).

Furthermore, learning & growth targeted that aspects such as employee motivation, employee training, and the capacity to develop specific employees required to implement the companies of new strategies (Osuagwu, et al., 2019)

5. CUSTOMER PERSPECTIVES

(Thuong & Singh, 2023) says Customer Perspectives is another part of the BSC and Rafiq et al. (2020) suggested that a customer’s perspective of SMEs in the BSC of customer perspectives that reveals positive impact thoughts about their satisfaction satisfactions of SMEs and the reinforces customer retention, and promotes customer acquisition Wakjira, G. G. (2023e). According to Naguit (2017), an enterprise’s internal business perspective is relative to the internal decisions and processes that are focused that providing added value for customers perspectives (Schulze et al., 2022) and Customer perspectives of SMEs of manufacturing textile and apparel industries is a key consideration for businesses customer enterprises in past scenario of SMEs and it deemed a significant impact requirements of SMEs (Yaskun et al., 2023). (Osuagwu, et al., 2019) says it focused that the life time of products and services targets with SMEs ability to deliver high-quality services and products activities that aligned to customer satisfaction and customer needs of SMEs (Girma et al., 2022) and an enterprise’s customer perspectives level is portrayed negatively and positively in its income and business profitability can be increase in manufacturing industries of SMEs (Yuliana and Kristiana, 2021).

Alternatively, SMEs business income and business profitability will increase as a result of heightened levels of employees and customer satisfaction related Wakjira, G. G., & Ibrahim, M. I. (2023) to its products and services of Manufacturing Textile industries of SMEs (Guidara & Khoufi, 2014).

6. CONCEPTUAL MODEL

Fig -1: Conceptual Model
Source: Developed by Researcher (2023)

7. METHODOLOGICAL INVESTIGATION

In quantitative data research the probability sampling methods and through the major types, from general to specific, to use a multi stage clustering it is often used to collect data a sample from population from

large, Geographically spread group of people of area of survey (Gritha Bhandari 2023) and stratified sampling methods the total populations will be dividend in to homogeneous groups of data survey will be used during study types, in the first stage, selected region was selected (Wakjira & Kant, 2023) conveniently, in second stage Manufacturing and service industry area or zone in the region as representative of the SMEs in Ethiopia will be selected (Hall et al. 2013).

Accordingly, at the first stage will be selected from region manufacturing industry area particularly, in Finfine area or Sheger City and East Shewa data will be selected as sample representative (Ayyagari et al., 2011; Lee et al., 2015). The selection criteria of this area were based on high density of manufacturing industry location in, Ethiopia (Chelliah et al., 2023). For this study, more than 384 respondents of Employee or workers from manufacturing industry CEO, CCO, CMO, and CFO on manufacturing textile and Apparel industry SMEs will be targeted as sample size that has been determined by using the following known formula (Cochran's 1977).

Where, n= is the sample size, z =is the selected critical value of desired confidence level, p= is the estimated proportion of an attribute that is present in the population, q=1-p and e= is the desired level of precision.

$$n = \frac{z^2pq}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{(1.96)^2(0.5)(0.5)}{(0.05)^2} = 384$$

Accordingly, 384 plus 15% in order to offset an anticipated low response or responded rate percent 10% to 20% and to maximize the generalizability of the results (Remenyi et al., 1998, Lai Van Voi 2023), 384x100/15=441 respondents were selected proportionally from both textile, garment and apparel manufacturing sectors in Ethiopia (Wakjira, 2023d).

Lists of Targeted area

Table -1: Lists of Targeted area of the study

Cluster		Sectors of targeted area	No of respondents
Bole Lami IP	1	Ever a top Sportswear textile PLC	54
	2	Top new Ethiopian Garment and textile PLC	39
	3	Ashton Textile Manufacturing PLC	41
	4	Vests Garment and Textile PLC	45
	5	Jay jay garment and textile Manufacturing PLC	60
	6	Shangtex garment and textile PLC	50
	7	Saints Ethiopian textile production PLC	47
Adama IP	1	King Dom Garment	35
	2	sunshine garment and textile PLC	30
	3	Jotun Garment, and textile Manufacturing PLC	40
Total			441

Source: Developed by researcher, 2023

8. DESCRIPTIVE MEASUREMENT DATA

The Descriptive Statistics of mean and Standard Deviation value in organizational Business Score Card implementation practice BSC dynamism in the Financial performance, Learning and Growth, Business Process and Customer Perspective activities in Manufacturing industry in SMEs and Organizational performance (Yaskun et al., 2023).

Table -2: Descriptive Measurement data

Financial Perspective (FP)	Measurements	N	Mean	S.E	S.D
Financial Perspective (FP)	Constantly seeking suitable planning	390	3.7462	.03797	.74975
	Utilizes financial resources well.	390	3.5615	.03738	.73827
	Solid financial plan.	390	3.5736	.04082	.80608
	Optimal finance in our enterprise.	390	3.8103	.04246	.83844
	Effective Administrative and operation costs	390	3.7410	.04194	.82824
	Effective cost minimization policies are	390	3.4538	.03448	.68094
	Internal Business (IB)	Measurements			
Internal Business (IB)	The internal process improves	390	3.7538	.03600	.71104
	To adapts to improve customer service	390	3.7897	.04497	.8543
	Sales processes are effective	390	3.6872	.04421	.87310
	Employees' opportunity to Challenge	390	3.5231	.02851	.56298
	Continuously improves	390	3.6821	.03373	.66606
	Improvement in the process flow	390	3.6821	.03672	.72519
	Learning and growth (LG)	Measurements			
Learning and growth (LG)	Continuous belief and invests	390	3.5641	.04078	.80534
	Employee Morale development	390	3.5359	.03729	.73648
	Employee willing to support	390	3.4564	.03797	.74991
	Employees professional development	390	3.6256	.04004	.79076
	Encourage employees	390	3.7949	.03860	.80301
	Employee innovation	390	3.6744	.03679	.72655
	Customer perspective	Measurements			
Customer perspective	To improve its market share.	390	3.7667	.03518	.69476

(CP)	To strives to improve its service and delivery	390	3.5667	.03286	.64884
	Current business solution.	390	3.8077	.03342	.66006
	To improve the quality of its goods and services	390	3.8974	.03626	.8045
	Returned a poor quality	390	3.5462	.03797	.74975
	Reduction of customer complaints	390	3.5115	.03738	.73827
Performance (P)	Measurements				
	Increased return on quality	390	3.6615	.03738	.73827
	Increase in operating profits	390	3.8436	.04082	.80608
	Effective Internal process management	390	3.5103	.04246	.83844
	Effective training Programme	390	3.7410	.04194	.82824
	Increase in the customer base number	390	3.5538	.03448	.68094
	Done better performance	390	3.6538	.03600	.71104

Source: Developed by Researcher (2023)

In this the Descriptive Statics result shown all Variables were conducted based on a 5- point Likert Scale. Respondents agreed that the Descriptive effect of BSC with Financial performance of Firm activities in SMEs Manufacturing Textile and apparel industry in Ethiopia BSC determinants in Financial performance highest mean results Optimal finance in our enterprise Mean value is (3.8103) with S. D Value .8344 (Yaskun et al., 2023), and the lowest Mean Financial performance measurement Effective cost minimization policies are the lowest Mean value (3.4538).

Overall the mean value output in assessments of Balanced Score card (BSC) (Schulze et al., 2022) in SMEs manufacturing and Apparel industry in Ethiopia are high mean value morethan (3.5) in the Implementation of BSC in Ethiopian industry are Because they have dissatisfied but rather tend to take challenges work activities, and engage in improving Business firm Performance, and business activities are still gap in Ethiopia (Meyer& Allen 2019).

In Business Process perspective of Textile and Apparel Industry of SMEs effect of BSC response of SMEs respondents that Respondents agreed that the Descriptive effect of BSC with Firm Performance of SMEs Manufacturing Textile and apparel industry in Ethiopia BSC determinants in Business process BSC performance activities highest mean results, to adapts to improve customer service Mean value is (3.8887) with S. D Value .8543 (Yaskun et al., 2023), and the lowest Mean Business process BSC performance activities measurement Employees' opportunity to Challenge are the lowest Mean value (3.5231).

Overall the mean value output in assessments of Balanced Score card (BSC) in SMEs manufacturing and Apparel industry in Ethiopia Business process BSC performance activities are high mean value morethan (3.5) in the Implementation of BSC in Ethiopian industry are, because they have dissatisfied but rather tend

to take challenges work activities, and engage in improving Business firm Performance, and business process activities are still gap in Ethiopia (Meyer& Allen 2019).

In Learning and Growth data stastics effect of BSC response of SMEs respondents that the respondents agreed that the Descriptive effect of BSC with Firm Performance of SMEs Manufacturing Textile and apparel industry in Ethiopia BSC determinants in Learning and growth highest mean results Optimal finance in our enterprise Mean value is (3.8949) with S. D Value .8301 (Yaskun et al., 2023), and the lowest Mean Learning and Growth measurement Employee willing to support are the lowest Mean value (3.4564).

Overall the mean value output in assessments of Balanced Score card (BSC) in SMEs manufacturing and Apparel industry in Ethiopia are high mean value morethan (3.5) in the Implementation of BSC in Ethiopian industry are Because they have dissatisfied but rather tend to take challenges work activities, and engage in improving Learning and growth firm Performance, and learning and growth activities are also still gap in Ethiopia (Meyer& Allen 2019).

In Customer perspective effect of BSC response of SMEs respondents that agreed that the Descriptive effect of BSC with Firm Performance of SMEs Manufacturing Textile and apparel industry in Ethiopia BSC determinants in Customer Perspectives highest mean results, to improve the quality of its goods and services Mean value is (3.8974) with S. D Value .8045 (Yaskun et al., 2023), and the lowest Mean Customer Perspectives measurement Reduction of customer complaints are the lowest Mean value (3.5115).

Overall the mean value output in assessments of Balanced Score card (BSC) in SMEs manufacturing and Apparel industry in Ethiopia are high mean value morethan (3.5) in the Implementation of BSC in Ethiopian industry (Schulze et al., 2022) are Because they have dissatisfied but rather tend to take challenges work activities, and engage in improving Customer Perspectives in industry of Business firm Performance, and business activities are still gap in Ethiopia (Meyer& Allen 2019).

Overall, the performance Measure, results statistics of Manufacturing Firm performance all indicators Mean value output result are also Morethan (3.5) value and it can be accepted in Manufacturing textile and Apparel industry of SMEs in Ethiopia are supported to measure.

9. CONCLUSIONS

In this the Descriptive Statics result shown all Variables were conducted based on a 5- point Likert Scale. Respondents agreed that the Descriptive effect of BSC with Financial performance of Firm activities in SMEs Manufacturing Textile and apparel industry in Ethiopia BSC determinants in Financial performance highest mean results Optimal finance in our enterprise Mean value is (3.8103) with S. D Value .8344, and the lowest Mean Financial performance measurement Effective cost minimization policies are the lowest Mean value (3.4538).

Overall the mean value output in assessments of Balanced Score card (BSC) in SMEs manufacturing and Apparel industry in Ethiopia are high mean value morethan (3.5) in the Implementation of BSC in Ethiopian industry are Because they have dissatisfied but rather tend to take challenges work activities, and engage in improving Business firm Performance, and business activities are still gap in Ethiopia (Meyer& Allen 2019).

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In Customer perspective effect of BSC response of SMEs respondents that agreed that the Descriptive effect of BSC with Firm Performance of SMEs Manufacturing Textile and apparel industry in Ethiopia BSC determinants in Customer Perspectives highest mean results, to improve the quality of its goods and services Mean value is (3.8974) with S. D Value .8045 (Yaskun et al., 2023), and the lowest Mean Customer Perspectives measurement Reduction of customer complaints are the lowest Mean value (3.5115).

10. RECOMMENDATIONS

This study had are some limitations in Ethiopian Manufacturing and Apparel Industry of SMEs are First, due to the limited availability of time, and other objectives this study collected data, and solicited opinions from enterprises, including those that had never applied the BSC in Manufacturing and Apparel industry in SMEs in their business management; therefore, in some cases the viewpoints will provided with low confidence but were still limited recourses and product Second, there was a lack of available date and untrained or un educated people that comparisons for the study.

This study has also only able to conduct gap of decision and research generally on Manufacturing and Apparel SMEs Industry but not separate industries, which would provide specific solutions for each specific industry within the Ethiopian Industry sector. Finally, this study that restricted the collection of data to in Central Cluster or head office only and it did not consider an overview of the whole of Full Manufacturing Industry in Ethiopia.

11. FUTURE DIRECTION RESEARCH

In the future researchers in Manufacturing and apparel industry of SMEs industry in Ethiopia may also examine how the performance of BSC in Firm performance that affects other operational levels, such as the top level , middle level , and operating levels of industry to be determine how much each level is affected.

Additionally, future practitioners study and researchers could implemented rely on this study to research study specific industries to compare and offer specific solutions for each industry when applying the BSC practice in management activities, management supporters, and business research activities. Prospective researchers could also study many different regions to determine the gap and how the application of the BSC performance in other public and private organization like Banks and Universities differs between geographical regions, and cultures and then offer appropriate solutions for each geographical region for Ethiopian businesses activities and perspectives.

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